

Place Names in Geography Education in Uganda: An Exploration of Teacher Trainees' Knowledge and Research Skills

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Abstract: *Teacher trainers assume that when students join the School of Education from high school they have basic knowledge and skills of the subjects they are expected to teach when they graduate as professional teachers. The main purpose of this study was to introduce the concept "Place Names" as a tool to help teacher trainees learn the geography of Kampala district in which their University is situated. Specifically the objectives were; to establish their understanding of the history, economy, social, cultural and human characteristics of local places in Kampala; to evaluate students' competences in research skills; to develop in teacher trainees' appreciation of the values of using place names in the teaching/learning of geography. Results show that teacher trainees are not aware of the geography of their surroundings outside the university campus. Teacher trainees have some knowledge and skills of research such as sketching maps, interviewing, observing and evaluation, which helped them to be well informed of their surroundings. This also helped them to understand the genesis, evolution and meaning of places. Conclusion; using place names as a strategy of teaching and learning geography, is a powerful tool in teacher education. Recommendation; The values of place names in teaching/learning geography should be exposed to students right from secondary schools to enable them understand their home environment consequently helping them internalize distant places globally.*

Key words: Place names, geography education, teacher trainee's knowledge and research skills.

Introduction:

To improve geography education the focus should be on teachers relying on them to make changes necessary to raise standards. Traditionally geography education of both secondary schools and tertiary institutions in Uganda is taught using traditional methods of lectures. Places/regions taught are described with help of atlases or by asking learners where certain towns, mountains, rivers etc are found. This approach doesn't offer motivation to learn about places because of lack of meaning attached to such places (Ramutsindela 1995). The essential role of memory in learning is most effective if students see the significance of place knowledge and encounter it in meaningful situations. Piaget (1969) considered learning as a search for meaning through accommodation of new information to earlier experiences. Through field study students are given opportunities to explore a place or local community using the following geographical roles: observation, speculation, analysis and evaluation. Mapping, sketching and photography help students develop observation skills. Through journal writing, interviewing, collecting artefacts, making rubbings are ways students can collect information (Rigs-Slater 1990). Field studies approach to learning geography is described by Resler and Kolivras (2009) as fun and an effective avenue for introducing students to methods in both human and physical geography. This study focuses on geography teacher trainees whose knowledge of place names in Kampala and the country as a whole, and their meanings is scanty. Through field work teacher trainees are given opportunities to explore, develop research skills which help them in getting meaning and values of such places.

However, due to budget constraints, field experience is generally on the decline in undergraduate geography education in many countries including Uganda. Resler and Kolivras (2009)

The concept place in Geography

Place names are our names for places in our own country or local names that local people have given or used to identify their places (Castner 1995). Places are social constructs evolving from on-going interaction and contestation understanding. This sense of place also requires understanding how that sense of place arose, for whom it exists and the implications of which it is preserved. Places exist because citizens in this place hold a shared sense of that place and act accordingly (Schmidt 2011). This implies people's lives are grounded in particular places; we come from a place, we live in a place and we preserve and exhibit pride over places. Places tell us so much about ourselves, our past and our propensity for change. Perkins et al (2010) adds on that identities and lives of individuals and peoples are rooted in particular places and in those human constructs called regions. Places are not static they change over time as a consequence of both physical and human processes which modify the earth's surface. Few places remain unchanged for long and these changes have a wide range of consequences (Riggs-Slater 1990) Murran (1990) adds "As knowledge ideologies, values reserves and technologies change, people make place altering decisions about how to use land, how to organise society and ways in which to relate, such as economically or politically to nearby and distant places. Places change in size

and complexity and in economic, political and cultural importance as networks of relationship between places are altered through expansion, changes in climate and other physical system” (pp 69)

Each place possesses a distinctive set of tangible and intangible characteristics that help to distinguish it from other places. Physical characteristics include climate, landforms, soils, hydrology vegetation and animal life. Their human characteristics include language, religion, political systems, economic systems, population distribution and quality of life.

Value of place names in Geography Education

It prepares students to think about places and the people who occupy and give meaning to it. Students think about themselves and others in the world, particularly how our identification with places affect how we understand people and places. This is personal identity, community identity and national identity rooted in a place and attachment to a place (Schmidt 2011; Murran 1990). Citizenship is one sense of self attached to places. This citizenship identity intentionally or unintentionally is developed in the geography classroom (Schmidt 2011). Santelmann et al (2011) argues that it provides opportunities for children to connect across generations to pass on local knowledge and develop an appreciation for the past. Students get first hand information of the outdoor environment in their local areas e.g. life experience of the previous generations in the place in which they live. Students learn about their local heritage. Barton (2012) refers to this as backyard geography; she argue that geography lecturers and teachers often times prioritize global issues at the expense of local backyard geography which has personal relevance than that of distant global issues

Students develop skills of observation, listening interviewing while studying places. Learning place names in the context of their language and culture may provide a rich source of tolerance and understanding and appreciating the uniqueness, role and position of other countries (Castner 1995). Students become aware of the interdependence movements that occur as a result. These include cultural movements such as trade and transportation, communications; the diffusion of ideas and people (migration) and spatial interaction. Weather systems like wind and water erosion, mass wasting etc are other examples which students get exposed to (NCGE 2000). Students start using their families, friends and neighbours as source of information. This exercise aids in the development of cultural literacy and multicultural competences (Forest 2002).

Research as a pedagogical approach to understanding places

Golightly (2010) argues that a constructivist view of knowledge and learning proposes that learners should be active independent students and should therefore critically examine the procedures of knowledge construction. The student in other words should be engaged in activities that

Map of Kampala City

require reasoning, discovering, problem solving, data gathering and analysis, application and communication of ideas. This approach stimulates learners to reflect, organise, analyse and solve problems. Field work is one method that enables students to acquire knowledge and skills in the process of learning.

Research through field work is recognised as an important essential component of geographical pedagogy (Hoalst-Pullen and Gatrell (2011). It is regarded as the most effective method of teaching and learning as opposed to the passive atmosphere of the traditionally lecture oriented university classrooms (Hoalst-Pullen 2011). He adds on that many students learn by doing and its approach allows them to get out into the community and grapple with complexity of real life challenges. Restriction of activity in the classroom produces an environment of aimless routine consequently it doesn't challenges students' thought. Value of fieldwork is that it fosters practical skills which can be applied in other situations e.g. making careful observations, creative writing skills, they practice focusing their attention, drawing skills, critical reflection thereby developing a personal sense of a place (Warkentin 2011)

Theoretical framework

I used problem-based learning, a theory advocated by Resler and Kolivras (2009) and Yeung (2010). It is an instructional approach that requires students to identify worthwhile problems for further exploration and deep analysis. It seeks to develop critical thinking skills about complex real life problems and associated with attitude that fosters inquiry and the ability to carry out systematic research. The students get to understand the relationship between the research process and the acquisition of primary data. They learn how to work in unfamiliar environments while developing an appreciation for place specific problems. The students are responsible for learning independently about the complicated situations. There is emphasis on development of self directedness, which incorporates the abilities to handle study tasks, monitor progress, make appropriate decisions in knowledge application and modify actions after critical reflection. Their learning process becomes much more enjoyable, appealing and rewarding than what are offered by traditional approaches of knowledge transmission. Values of problem based learning include retention of knowledge, concept and skills in the long term and opportunity of social interaction through interviews with village elders. Learning goes far beyond the recall of knowledge and reproduction or responding passively to given situations (Keenan and Fontaine 2012). Knowledge learned during lectures and from tests is demystified and concept learned from the classrooms can be integrated with knowledge gained during fieldwork. Lecturers change their roles from information providers to facilitators, guides, coaches and learners and collaborators.

Context of Kampala city

Kampala is the largest city and capital of Uganda. It is divided into five administrative areas. Kampala Central Division, Kawempe division, Makindye division, Nakawa division and Lubaga division (Nagadya 2007). It is spread over more than twenty hills. It is one of the fastest growing cities in Africa. Its architecture is a mixture of the modern, the colonial and the Indian. It is situated at an attitude of 1.180 m above sea level. To the south are Lake Victoria the world’s second largest fresh water lake and the source of the longest river in the world, the river Nile. The swamps between hills were habitant for impala and other members of the antelope family. The animals grazed on the slopes of the hills and came down to the swamps for water. According to Nagadya (2007) the king turned it into

his hunting grounds. The word *impala* was the English name for particular antelope family. So the British referred to the area s “The hill of the Impala”, which the Buganda translated into Luganda as “Kasozi Kampala” and eventually Kampala From a small hamlet occupying 19 sq km, it had spread to seven hills by 1962 coming the tag “City of seven hills”. The original seven hills are; Mengo, Rubaga, Namirembe, Makerere, Kololo, Nakasero and Old Kampala. Nakasero is the administrative centre and the wealthiest residential area. In 2001 the city units were substantially expanded to include many of the surrounding communities within the city, Namirembe, Nakulabye, Kasubi, Bwaise, Kawempe, Kikaaya, Mpererwe, Lubaga, Nateete, Busega, Mutundwe, Ndeeba,

Katwe, Kibuli, Kabalagala, Ntinda, Kiwatule, Nagulu, Bugolobi, Mbuya, Luzira, Port Bell and Butabika.

Today greater Kampala stands on at least 21 hills. The prominent hills that form the modern day capital and their signature to the city's political and social economic life are Old Kampala, Mengo Hill, Namirembe Hill, Rubaga Hill, Nakasero Hill, Kololo Hill, Kibuli Hill, Makerere Hill, Biziga Hill, Muyenga Hill, Mutundwe Hill, Mutungo Hill, Kireka Hill, Makindye Hill, and Banda Hill.

Climate: Kampala has a tropical wet and dry climate. It has two annual wet seasons. There is a long rainy season from February through June and a short one from August through December due to the city's higher altitudes, average temperatures are cooler than what is been in other cities with this type of climate. Kampala has a diverse ethnic population although the Baganda, the local ethnic group make up to over 60% of the greater Kampala region.

Statement of the problem

Most of the lecturers at the School of Education use a lecture format to teach students. The lecturer stands in front of the class talking or ask some questions. This method renders transmission of knowledge in a passive manner. Its value is that it is efficient, occurs in a normal class period and suitable for large classes. This method is no longer relevant since students have access to multiple sources of geographical information if properly guided. One way of understanding places is to examine the physical environment, the people who live there and the identities they hold, how they describe those identities, from where they arise and what these identities mean to people. Kampala city's size, culture, political, history, social and economic activities change over time but this is little known by students. Geography students at the university come from all parts of Uganda and other neighbouring countries and have little knowledge of the geography of their capital Kampala located on over twenty two (22) hills. Research as a pedagogical approach to teaching and learning enables students to best understand the region (place) by assessing multiple source of information. However students get exposed to research methods in a theoretical approach and have little or no opportunity to practice research skills in a real situation. The concept "place" central to geography education as a teaching/ learning strategy is also used sparingly by teacher trainers and secondary school teachers.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study was to help students understand and explain the nature of places found in Kampala city through research.

Objectives of the study

To establish teacher trainees' knowledge of places in Kampala.

To evaluate teacher trainee research skills

To help teacher trainees appreciate the value of teaching and learning through place names.

Methodology

The geography class of 2nd year) was big with over 100 teacher trainees. The class was divided into groups of five people each. A list of places in Kampala city was provided to the students in the introductory lesson and each group selected

a place they were going to study. This activity was done in three weeks whereby students studied/collected data on landforms and other physical elements of the place, the settlements, population and resources, environmental issues, politics, industries and the relationships between these geographical aspects. The researchers hoped to develop in teacher trainees values of problem solving, critical thinking, distribution learning, team building and information technologies as suggested by Hoalst and Gatrell (2011). They add on that this skill centred learning paradigm, promotes collaborative learning, and promotes abstract reasoning, data synthesis and data analysis skills. Although the lecturers guided them throughout the three weeks, it helped teacher trainees abandon the teacher dependent model of classroom, to learning through observations, interviewing, consulting the library, etc which was interactive group learning. The teacher trainees were encouraged to draw sketch maps, graphs, cross-sections. The researchers supervised students in the field and responded to calls for help. At the end of the three weeks a group report was compiled and handed in. The teacher trainees were requested to add on one paragraph on what they had learnt through this exercise

Presentation of data

First objective; Establish teacher trainees knowledge of place names in Kampala

Teacher Trainees Knowledge

Location of places in Kampala City.

Very few 2 student groups tried to situate the places studied;

The place is located between Rubaga Hill and Mutundwe

. The place is located between the valley between Mulago and Makerere hills

Apart from the above two groups others did not mention anything or grid references or longitudes and latitudes.

A good number described the deteriorating nature the physical environment; massive erosion from both hills leading to the blocking of the channels. *The channels are blocked with soil, water bottles, polythene bags, clothes, animal and human wastes.*

The poor waste disposal in the city was described by all groups'

Urban farming; *growing crops like bananas, yams, sugar cane, maize and cassava is common. These gardens are dominantly in swampy areas or residents with big plots grow bananas in their compound.*

Domestic animals are reared in Kampala outside the CBD. These include cows and goats which are seen on most streets just outside the centre/heart of Kampala. Some cows are raised in enclosures/shelter and are fed on grass and other food supplements. Some people with ample space raise chicken for commercial purposes these include broilers and layers, whose products are sold for markets/shops around

Non-agricultural activities

Brick making using clay found in most of the swamps in the valleys between hills, running retail shops either in kiosks, shops or markets stalls where a city council markets are found, food vending especially cooked good for breakfast lunch and evening meals.

These are located near city centre, the universities, and private halls of residence (Hostels), there are also guest houses, motels for business men especially those from distant places.

Brewing local beer, gin from millet, sorghum, cassava, bananas etc is the most common activity in the slums.

There are wholesale shops as well as retail shops in the big suburbs like Ntinda. Natete, Namuwongo, Katwe etc Carpentry and blacksmithing, and welding activities in the slums was reported by five groups

Car washing is a common activity all over Kampala.

Stone quarrying at Muyenga, Nakawa etc.

Craft making and drums making in Nsambya/Kabalagala. area

Tourist recreation in some areas; green parks and hotels.

Grain Milling industries of Kisenyi near Balikuddembe market.

Residents and House types

Students also recognized presence of slums in Katanga, Kivulu, Kamwokya etc characterized by poor housing, one roomed family homes, some building materials are; mud and wattle, sanitation is very poor with open sewer, water is expensive for slum dweller, lack of electricity yet fuel wood and charcoal are also expensive. There is congestion also in some places there. There is urban renewal taking place e.g. Namuwongo. The slums near universities are being transformed slowly by construction of magnificent hostels and shopping malls e.g. Katanga, Kikoni.

Land tenure

The teacher trainees reported the following categories of land tenure systems.

Government land especially the central district area, most of the land to the west, North and East belongs to the King of Buganda, individual church land and the Muslim, as well as traditional rulers. The majority of the poor live in the swampy valleys belonging to the Central government, squatters on the kings land or renting from rich landlords.

Social services: A number of mosques, churches and other religious places, schools and medical centers are available throughout the region and were mentioned by students their reports

The people

Most people in the places studied by the students are occupied the Baganda ethnic group, the rest are a mixture of Basoga, Ankole, Banyoro, Langi, Acholi etc. Unemployment and crime rate is high among these slum dwellers, malnutrition among children, child labor (children work instead of attending school e.g. fetching water for families, picking scrap metal for sale, lifting heavy goods for people, catering in restaurants or domestic use.

Pollution

No latrines, domestic wastes are thrown anywhere in the open sewer, bad smell where there is stagnant waters, some water channels are blocked by wastes or soil eroded from either side of the valleys. Source of water for most slum dwellers are springs which might be a distance from their residences. People have low levels of education or no education at all. Some women are prostitutes or thieves, work in security ie. private security organizations. These people grow their own food, rear chicken, goats or sheep.

Areas mentioned by students for high unemployment levels include Mengo-Kisenyi, Banda, Kalerwe, Bwaise, Namuwongo, Kibuli etc. People do some work like metal fabrication, making charcoal stoves, source pans, bicycle spares, kettle, motor spares, maize mills etc. They do gambling, put up false roadblocks to rob people. There is drug abuse, alcoholism and high crime rate.

History of the places

There are various reasons for places to be given names; there are places given names related to activities in that place.

“**Kirombe**” is a name given to a place where clay is mined for brick making

“**Nkuzongere**” is a place where a man used to clean white ants by removing their wings one day a ghost stood behind him and asked “*can I give you more ants to clean?*” This in the local language is “Nkuzongere”

Places named after important people

Namaganda named after the King’s wife with that name and was buried in that place

Masajja was a place where courageous, brave and determined hunters lived. It was a forest full of wild dangerous animals, with a swamp nearby. Today it is a suburb of Kampala.

Katimbo is a place named after a political leader, country chief lived. He was famous for being generous to the local people as well as being a government worker.

Names after physical features

“**Lusaka**” a place with thickest, shrubs and tall grass., in local language, this type of vegetation is called; Kasaka

Kalagala – means green color. This place was covered with evergreen trees, grass on the hills and valleys.

There are also names named after animals for example

“**Nkere**” this was a place with many frogs which used to make noise at night.

Nalukolongo is a place located in swampy area and used to have lung fish in large numbers. This fish is locally called Nkolongo and the swamp before it was cleared for industries was a habitat for this fish.

Migration to urban areas from rural areas and from distant places has given rise to certain places being named after dominant groups of people. For example

“**Katanga**” a place between Mulago and Makerere hills was dominantly occupied by Congolese from the neighboring country west of Uganda. These Congolese used to sell gold and diamonds in Kampala city. This slum was named “Katanga” because of the dominance of these Congolese from Katanga a place where a variety of minerals are mined in D.R Congo

Kizungu is another place in Kampala which is occupied by white people. These white people in the local language here are called Bazungu and the place is called “Kizungu”

There are places named after cultural activities for example

Mengo Kisenyi Church Zone There is a popular Catholic Church in this place opened by Pope Paul II in 1969.

Mbare” a place which is now a forest was a burial place and there is a shrine built by the founder of this village. It is currently a place of worship belonging to traditional religious shrines.

Namilyango was a place which had a shrine with many doors. In the local language – Luganda a door is called mulyango but

because of the many doors (9) it is called Namilyango for plural. Today there is a catholic mission in this place with schools and churches etc.

Kitagonerwa, is a name given to a place where it was believed that one must not snore while sleeping. There was a traditional religious shrine where gods met at night to plan for activities of the following day. One day, the people over-slept and started snoring and didn't hear the earthquake coming even its movement did not awake them resulting in destruction and death of people.

The students in our interaction after this research were excited and happy to discover the history behind these place names.

Research skills

Many students used interviews to get the above information. They used observations to record the landforms, nature of soil erosion between the hills where they did the research. The settlements, house types and materials used for house construction were recorded. The foot paths, the gravel and tarmac roads were noted by teacher trainees. The people, their quality of life, their survival activities like cultivation, brewing and selling local beer and spirits, kiosks brick making well are observed by the students.

Some drew sketch maps and cross-sections; some were able to take photographs while others were able to add information from the library.

Many of them confessed that it was their first time to practice what they learnt from the research methods class.

Student's appreciation of the value of teaching and learning through places.

Motivation and Inspiration acquired by teacher trainees from exercise include;

I realized, places are points of analysis of geographical phenomena, the physical environment, human geography as well as political geography.

There were teacher trainees who felt that they learnt practical skills which they learnt in theory "I practiced skills which I learnt in theory.

I practiced skills of observation and analysis of geographical phenomena in the place where I did research.

I learnt the skills of drawing and sketching of maps as well as map reading.

The local council chairman had a map and we also borrowed an atlas from the neighboring school.

Some students were satisfied with their work and said "*I proved to be a good researcher; I discovered the origin of my village,*

I improved my skills of language writing and interviewing.

I learnt that place names arise out of culture, languages and attitudes of people have over that place.

I learnt that place names have strong relationship with practical part of geography like fieldwork when you study details of particular place.

I internalized the roles of local council chairman and other committee members. In a village

I acquired friends whom I interviewed through face to face interviews. These people gave us a lot of information about their lives and we really benefited a lot using this method of research.

I got exposed to village elders, important people linked to community development

I learnt organizational skills by selecting relevant facts from a lot of information collected.

Acquired skills of identifying geographical phenomena and extending classroom study in reality.

I realized that learning geography is not confined only in classrooms setting but outside as well.

I got to realize that people in their villages feel comfortable and happy in their

Environment without thinking of going anywhere else where they could get better

basic amenities

I acquired skills of associating and cooperating with my peers since the fieldwork was done in a group.

Discussion

Learning and teaching geography through fieldwork is essential and emphasized by many scholars, Krakowka (2012) Barton 1012, Fontaine and Keanran 2012, Rester and Kolivra 2009. However due to reduced funding to secondary and higher institutions of learning by Uganda government (Kagoda 2011) geography students are not exposed to learning through fieldwork. The researcher used place names to help students learn their environment in this case a detailed study of Kampala the capital city of Uganda which they hardly know. Place names introduced to the students wide reaching aspects of knowledge, culture, history, local geographical information and many other aspects of geography (Castner 1995) The knowledge of places of Kampala, forty two (42) places, studied in details by the teacher trainees was appreciated by students through sharing during class time, and through the reports handed in. The urban social economic status is revealed to the students, in that while the poor live in valleys of Kampala and survive by farming, while the rich live on the slopes and top of the hills of Kampala. The house types and building materials also differ according to the social economic status of the people and the land tenure system

Students realized that there is urban agriculture mainly carried out by the poor in the slums where they live. They grow beans, sweet potatoes etc. However, even the urban rich grow some food. Animals like cows, goats, and sheep, chicken are raised, which some students never expected in an urban environment. Farmers' markets are another economic activity little known to students. The histories, religion, politics of certain places in Kampala were all fully explored by some students. This confirms Castner (1995) argument that "local names are striking, revealing and useful in them selves and studying them will encourage profitable experience in teaching about foreign places and will lead to improving and expanding our understanding of them.

Knowledge of transport system and other modern communication like phones are mentioned by at least twenty groups. They related it to connection with other places. The characteristics of places; students mentioned the slopes and swampy places. Rainwater as agent of soil erosion in this hilly region, was mentioned by all groups The human activities, their belief systems, economic activities, the different ethnic groups, languages used were described by students confirming

Murray's (1990) argument that "Places provide learning opportunities to students.

Research

Riggs – Salter 1990 believe that "Places tell us so much about ourselves, our past and prosperity to change fieldwork and research are opportunities for students to explore a city or their local community using four geographical tools, observation, speculation analysis, and evaluation. Mapping, sketching and photography help develop student's observation skills. Journal writing and interviewing are other tools of collecting data. In the case of Teacher trainers, they all used the above methods, most of them for the first time. Very few drew sketch maps and photographs. Journal writing is an activity not fully used in the university therefore no student used this method.

This exploration of Kampala city through research helped the students develop a geographic perspective of urban functions and characteristics of places in the city.

Value of Teaching and learning geography through places

National Council for Geographic Education (NCGE), (Geography for life) (1994) emphasizes the fact that places are human creations and geographers must understand the genesis, evolution and meaning of places. This actually motivated teacher trainees to learn more as they discovered the history behind the places of Kampala. Many students noted the changing nature of places through interviews, e.g changing nature of settlements as new roads are constructed in the city of Kampala. This confirms NCGE, (Geography for life) (1995) findings that "few places remain unchanged for long and those changes have a wide range of consequences; knowledge, values, resources and technologies change, while people make place altering decisions about how to use land, how to organize society and ways to relate to economic or political issues to nearby and distant places.

Geography teacher trainees appreciated that opportunity to practice research skills and interact with local people in the places they studied. This was the first time this kind of research and fieldwork was done, that is a detailed study of a place for three weeks. Through class discussion the teacher trainees hoped to use the same approach of field work when they graduate.

The geography of places surrounding the university and distant places within Kampala city was explored. Anderson and Fitzpatrick 2011 ideas of places is confirmed; "*engaging with real-life information helps students build and contextualize content knowledge in multiple disciplines, like agriculture, religion, environment issues, politics, history etc. as well as study skills.* Skills of teamwork, critical analysis, and practical skills were acquired by teacher trainers, and were appreciated as well. This kind of opportunity is rare in secondary schools and university education.

Conclusion

The student knowledge of Kampala city was enriched through research of selected number of places (42). The teacher trainees acquired knowledge of the physical and human characteristics of places. This included the land forms, vegetation and climate. They acquired more information about the history of places in Kampala, the different ethnic groups, settlements, congestion in slums, the poor and rich and how they survive.

The teacher trainees had the opportunity to put in practice the research skills they normally learn in the lecture rooms. Through group work, teamwork and peer teaching effective learning took place.

The teacher trainees appreciated learning about Kampala city through place names. They were motivated by their interaction with the people in the places where they did their research. Through interviews they learnt the history and culture of the people and the changing nature of places. They hoped to use the same approach in geography classes when they graduate as teachers.

Recommendations

Teacher educators should endeavor to expose their students to interactive methods of training students to enable them learn effectively. Place names as a point of analysis of geographic knowledge and skills is a tool that should be effectively utilized to develop research skills of teacher trainees

Research develops in student's skills of data collection through observation, interviewing, document analysis, photographs etc. Geography teacher trainers should integrate such interactive approaches to learning in their teaching

In-service courses should be organized for geography teachers in secondary schools so that this approach to geography education is embraced to make the subject attractive to students at that level

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